

Introducing oRAGinality: a RAG-based approach to measure scientific originality with LLMs

Diogo Machado*

Technopolis Group

June 19, 2026

Abstract

Large language models (LLMs) are being rapidly incorporated into research evaluation, yet evidence shows systematic underperformance on novelty assessment and, beyond performance, a directional preference against novel work. Two mechanisms underlie this failure. First, in next-token prediction on a static training corpus, LLMs cannot reliably delimit what counts as prior art for a given focal text. Second, without external grounding, novelty judgements tend to favour familiar, lower-risk ideas, since most scientific work is incremental and LLMs favour the majority class. Both mechanisms point to the same remedy, which is to ground novelty assessment in a systematic, temporally valid body of prior art and a strict comparative rubric. We introduce oRAGINALITY, a retrieval-augmented generation approach that embeds each focal title and abstract with SPECTER2 and retrieves the ten most semantically similar works published before the focal text’s date from a corpus of more than 170 million publications, identified from semantic content rather than from reference lists. An LLM then scores novelty by comparing the focal text against the retrieved prior art under an explicit rubric. On 1,252 FWF proposals, oRAGINALITY attains high precision against human peer reviewers, and a blinded re-examination suggests many apparent misses reflect human over-estimation of novelty caused by incomplete prior art. Six independent domain experts manually audited a sample of these cases and confirmed that the retrieval-grounded rationales are informative and that, in the great majority of cases, the lower novelty scores are justified. As a further test, proposals from the FWF 1000 Ideas programme, designed to attract high-risk, high-reward ideas, receive systematically higher novelty scores than those from FWF’s standard funding stream within the same field and year, providing external support for the measure independent of peer-review labels.

Keywords: novelty indicators; large language models; retrieval-augmented generation; research evaluation; peer review; science policy

1 Introduction

Generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) has moved, within a few years, from a speculative tool to a part of the everyday infrastructure of science, and the frontier now being crossed is its use in research evaluation itself (Ding et al., 2025; Frontiers, 2025). GenAI is already being used to interrogate the evaluation process from the inside. In a process evaluation of the FWF Emerging Fields programme, for instance, it has been deployed to analyse how peer reviewers prioritise and operationalise assessment criteria such as quality, novelty, and relevance (Kolarz and Machado,

*Corresponding author: diogo.machado@technopolis-group.com. ORCID: 0000-0001-6147-876X.

2025). The promise is efficiency, enabling faster triage, lower reviewer burden, and more consistent rubrics. The risk is more subtle and, for the long-run productivity of science, more consequential. A recurring concern across recent studies is that LLMs handle *novelty* poorly. Focus-level analyses of LLM-generated reviews find that models concentrate on technical facets such as method and validity and rarely raise novelty as a weakness, even when human reviewers do (Shin et al., 2025); fine-grained studies of review text report declining attention to originality and critical reasoning as LLM use spreads (Wu et al., 2026). Furthermore, work on AI-assisted grant writing documents that AI-edited proposals win funding more often yet are more homogeneous, resembling past winners and yielding fewer high-impact outcomes (Qian et al., 2026; Kozlov, 2026).

In prior work, we showed that this is not only a performance problem but a *preference* problem. In a small but information-dense sample of research proposals, an LLM-based selection process agreed with human funding decisions in 60% of cases, but the residual disagreement was not random. It concentrated on the novelty dimension and in a single direction. The model was systematically less willing than human reviewers to fund highly novel proposals (Machado, 2026). Separately, embedding-based work demonstrated that novelty can be recovered remarkably well from the geometry of scientific text, that is, from the semantic relationship between a focal contribution and its prior art (Machado, 2025). Read together, these two results are suggestive. If the problem is a preference that pulls judgements toward the statistical mainstream, and if the signal needed to assess novelty lives in the semantic distance to prior art, then the way to improve LLM novelty assessment is to remove the model’s discretion over what prior art is and to force the comparison to be explicit.

We argue that LLM underperformance on novelty has two reinforcing roots. *(i) Time.* LLMs have no reliable internal clock. They cannot consistently determine, for a given focal text, which works should count as prior art (relevant preceding works) because temporal ordering is not faithfully encoded in next-token training. *(ii) Preference.* The training objective rewards proximity to the statistical centre, so when a model is left to judge novelty “in the abstract”, it falls back on a learned, risk-averse notion of what good work looks like (Bender et al., 2021). Both roots admit the same fix: *operationalise* the task. Supply the model with a systematically retrieved and temporally valid set of prior art, and constrain its judgement with a strict rubric that ties the novelty score to concrete content overlap between the focal text and that prior art. The assessment then becomes a verifiable comparison rather than an exercise of preference, and it becomes reproducible, auditable, and hard to game.

A small but growing literature has begun to operationalise scientific novelty assessment with retrieval-augmented LLMs. Lin et al. (2025) introduce SchNovel and RAG-Novelty, evaluating whether LLMs can identify the more novel paper in pairs of arXiv publications when supplied with retrieved neighbouring abstracts. Shahid et al. (2025) develop a literature-grounded novelty checker for scientific ideas, combining retrieval, filtering, reranking, and LLM comparison against expert-labelled novelty judgements. More recently, Zhang et al. (2026) propose an agentic system that extracts claimed contributions from papers, retrieves related prior work, and produces evidence-backed novelty reports based on contribution-level comparisons. These studies mark an important shift away from asking LLMs to judge novelty in the abstract and toward grounding novelty judgements in explicit prior art.

Yet they also leave open the setting that motivates this paper. Existing systems focus primarily on papers or generated ideas rather than real funding-agency proposals. They also differ from the measurement design developed here in two ways. First, they do not establish novelty against a transparent, deterministic, large-scale prior-art universe. One uses a small benchmark corpus of arXiv papers; another retrieves literature for idea-checking without defining a fixed population-scale search universe; and another depends on an external semantic search backend whose coverage

and ranking procedure are not specified as part of the measurement design. By contrast, our ORAGINALITY approach (a contraction of *RAG* and *originality*) defines the search space ex ante as more than 170 million publication title–abstract records and retrieves prior art deterministically using exact cosine similarity within that fixed corpus. Second, existing systems are not benchmarked against human novelty assessments made in an actual funding process. Their validation relies instead on paper-pair assumptions, small expert-labelled sets of ideas, or qualitative paper-review evidence. By contrast, ORAGINALITY is evaluated on real scientific proposals submitted to a funding agency and benchmarked against the novelty scores assigned by human peer reviewers. It therefore tests not only whether an LLM can produce a plausible novelty judgement, but whether a retrieval-grounded novelty measure agrees with, challenges, and in some cases improves upon the novelty judgements produced by the peer-review system itself.

We apply ORAGINALITY to the assessment of funding proposals, the setting where research evaluation carries the highest stakes, though the method applies equally to retrospective novelty measurement. For each focal text we build an individualised body of prior art via retrieval-augmented generation (Lewis et al., 2020). We embed the focal title and abstract with SPECTER2 (Cohan et al., 2020; Singh et al., 2023), compute cosine similarity against a corpus of more than 170 million publications, and retain the ten most similar works published before the focal text’s date. An LLM (GPT-5.1) then assigns a novelty score by comparing the focal text against this retrieved prior art under an explicit rubric. A central design choice is that prior art is identified from *semantic content*, never from the focal text’s own reference list, for reasons we develop in Section 3.3.

We make three contributions. First, we propose a deterministic, large-scale operationalisation of novelty measurement. Rather than asking an LLM to judge novelty in the abstract, ORAGINALITY fixes the prior-art universe ex ante as more than 170 million publication title–abstract records, retrieves temporally valid neighbours using exact semantic similarity, and constrains the model to compare the focal text with that retrieved prior art under an explicit rubric. Because prior art is defined relative to the date of each focal text, the method can be applied prospectively to support proposal evaluation and peer review, and retrospectively to measure the novelty of past applications, funded projects and publications. It can therefore support not only ex ante assessment, but also monitoring, evaluation, and portfolio analysis by funding agencies. Second, we provide, to our knowledge, the first evaluation of a RAG-based novelty measure on real funding-agency proposals with human peer-review novelty scores as the benchmark. We apply ORAGINALITY to 1,252 FWF individual-project proposals and assess how well it identifies proposals judged highly novel by reviewers. As an external validation test, we also compare two FWF funding streams, one standard and one explicitly designed for highly novel and high-risk ideas, and ask whether ORAGINALITY assigns higher novelty scores to the latter. Third, we examine the cases in which ORAGINALITY and human reviewers disagree. Using a blinded re-examination of these disagreements, we show that many apparent machine “misses” are likely human over-ratings of novelty caused by incomplete prior-art retrieval on the human side, precisely the failure mode that ORAGINALITY is designed to address. We further validate this interpretation through a manual audit by six independent domain experts, who assess the retrieval-grounded rationales directly.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section 2 develops the conceptual background. Section 3 describes the ORAGINALITY pipeline, including the case against reference-based prior art and the scoring rubric. Section 4 presents the data. Section 5 reports the first-pass classification results, the blinded re-examination of disagreements, and a manual expert audit of disagreement cases. Section 6 presents the validation test against the FWF 1000 Ideas programme. Section 7 discusses implications and limitations, and Section 8 concludes.

2 Conceptual background

2.1 Why novelty is hard for statistical learners

Novelty is intrinsically distributional. Truly novel work, by definition, departs from the patterns that dominate the existing corpus. Autoregressive LLMs are trained to predict likely continuations of a sequence, and their parameters encode recurring associations among ideas, methods, and framings in the training data. When asked to judge novelty without external grounding, their outputs may therefore be pulled toward configurations that are statistically familiar (Bender et al., 2021). This is the optimisation target, not a defect; but it has a predictable consequence at the tails of the distribution, where rare and unprecedented concepts enjoy the weakest statistical support. When such a model is asked to judge novelty without external grounding, it may favour proposals that resemble previously successful work over proposals that depart more strongly from established patterns (Machado, 2026).

This compounds a conservatism already present in human peer review, which is known to penalise unconventional work in both funding and publication (Boudreau et al., 2016; Lane et al., 2022; Stephan et al., 2017). This conservatism is itself a recognised science-policy problem. Novelty is the marker of high-risk/high-reward research, and an over-reliance on conventional metrics has been shown to reinforce risk-aversion in funding, which has motivated dedicated novelty indicators for the monitoring and evaluation of such research (Machado, 2021). The policy-relevant question is therefore not whether LLMs are biased against novelty in some absolute sense, but whether they add bias in the same direction as human review. If they do, augmenting or replacing human review with LLM review is not neutral; it compounds.

2.2 Two diagnosable failure modes: time and preference

We distinguish two mechanisms behind LLM novelty failure because they imply different remedies.

Time. Assessing novelty requires a baseline that defines what is known at the moment a focal idea is proposed. LLMs do not represent time faithfully (Zhu et al., 2025). Their parametric knowledge mixes works from many periods without a reliable ordering, and they cannot be trusted to restrict “prior art” to what genuinely predates a focal text. A model may judge an idea unremarkable because similar work now exists, even if that work post-dates the proposal. Such an anachronism can lead the model to misjudge novelty systematically, with the risk likely to be greater for older texts than for recent ones. Any operational measure must therefore impose temporal validity externally.

Preference. Even with the right time window, an unconstrained model applies an implicit, risk-averse notion of merit. Left to “decide what counts as novel”, it imports the central-tendency preference described above. The remedy is to remove discretion by fixing the comparison set, and replace the open-ended judgement with a rubric that maps observable content overlap to a score.

ORAGINALITY addresses both mechanisms directly by grounding the exercise and providing narrow instructions with a clear novelty rubric. Retrieval restricted to pre-dating publications resolves the time problem by construction. An explicit, content-anchored rubric resolves the preference problem by making the score a function of how much the focal text overlaps with concretely identified prior art, rather than of the model’s taste. The embedding-based result that novelty tracks semantic distance to prior art (Machado, 2025) is what makes this operationalisation viable. The retrieved set does not merely provide context; the retrieval itself constitutes the measurement instrument.

3 The oRAGinality approach

3.1 Overview

For a focal text d (a proposal or a paper) with title t_d , abstract a_d , and date τ_d , ORAGINALITY proceeds in three steps:

1. **Represent.** Encode (t_d, a_d) into a document embedding $\mathbf{v}_d \in \mathbb{R}^k$ using SPECTER2.
2. **Retrieve prior art.** Compute cosine similarity between \mathbf{v}_d and the embeddings of a reference corpus of approximately 173 million publications, restrict candidates to those published before τ_d , and keep the top $K = 10$ by similarity as the focal text’s prior art \mathcal{P}_d .
3. **Assess.** Prompt an LLM (GPT-5.1) with (t_d, a_d) and the titles and abstracts of \mathcal{P}_d , under a fixed novelty rubric, and obtain a novelty score with a justification.

3.2 Representation and retrieval

We use SPECTER2 (Singh et al., 2023), a scientific-document embedding model that builds on the citation-informed SPECTER architecture (Cohan et al., 2020), to encode the concatenation of title and abstract. For each focal text we score candidates by cosine similarity,

$$\text{sim}(d, p) = \frac{\mathbf{v}_d \cdot \mathbf{v}_p}{\|\mathbf{v}_d\| \|\mathbf{v}_p\|}, \quad (1)$$

and define the retrieved prior art as

$$\mathcal{P}_d = \underset{p: \tau_p < \tau_d}{\text{top-K}} \text{ sim}(d, p), \quad K = 10. \quad (2)$$

The temporal constraint $\tau_p < \tau_d$ is critical. It guarantees that the comparison set is genuine prior art and enables the LLM to focus completely on the novelty assessment task instead of devoting reasoning attention to processing the time dimension. When publication dates are missing, we rely on publication year which is always available. When the publication date is the 1st of January, that typically means the date is missing, so we take a conservative approach and do not use them as prior art when in the same year as each focal proposal.

The SPECTER2 embedding representations of prior art are sourced from Semantic Scholar (S2) and OpenAlex. Our analysis covers a set of approximately 173 million vector representations, without conditioning on publication year, time period, or topic area. We compute exact pairwise cosine similarities rather than relying on dimensionality reduction, indexing, or an approximate inner-product search for acceleration. This design choice prioritises reproducibility and numerical transparency, ensuring that similarity scores are deterministic and not affected by approximation settings, index construction, or retrieval heuristics. With our sample of 1252 proposal texts, this means that we computed over 200 billion exact cosine similarities.

3.3 Why not the focal text’s own references

A natural alternative would be to take the works *cited* by the focal text as its prior art. We deliberately avoid this. Citation-based prior art makes the novelty measure depend on referencing behaviour rather than on the content of the idea, and that dependence is problematic for four reasons.

1. **Heterogeneous referencing practices.** Fields, periods, teams, and publication venues differ systematically in how, how much, and what they cite. A novelty measure built on reference lists would inherit these differences and conflate them with novelty, penalising or rewarding texts for conventions that have nothing to do with how original their ideas are.
2. **Gameability.** Reference lists are trivial to manipulate. An author can inflate an apparent novelty score by omitting or hiding closely overlapping prior work, or by padding the list with distant references, so that the same idea can be made to look more or less original at will.
3. **GenAI contamination.** The diffusion of generative AI is producing fabricated or distorted references and is shifting referencing practice in ways that would propagate directly into any reference-based novelty assessment (Zhao et al., 2026).
4. **Strategic citation behaviour.** Well-documented practices such as citation cartels and coercive or reciprocal citation further decouple reference lists from the actual intellectual novelty of a contribution (Kojaku et al., 2021).

Identifying prior art from *semantic content* via retrieval avoids all four problems. The comparison set is constructed the same way for every text, independent of citation conventions; it is systematic in that the same retrieval process applies to every text, surfacing the most similar prior work regardless of whether the author chose to cite it. Moreover, it is hard to game, because the only way to change the retrieved prior art and hence the novelty score is to change the content of the idea itself.

3.4 LLM novelty assessment and rubric

Given the focal text and its retrieved prior art, the model is asked to assess the degree of overlap and to assign a novelty level according to an explicit rubric. The rubric is the central piece of operationalisation. It specifies what each novelty level means in terms of concrete relationships between the focal text and \mathcal{P}_d (e.g. method reuse, recombination of known elements, problem novelty, or genuine conceptual departure), and it requires the model to justify the score by reference to specific items of prior art.

Listing 1: Novelty-assessment prompt and rubric (system + user message).

```
SYSTEM_PROMPT = """ You are an expert evaluator of scientific novelty.
You assign a novelty score from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high) to a
focal proposal text provided by the user, based on comparison with its
10 closest prior papers. You use the rubric provided by the user to
determine the score.

RUBRIC (apply exactly as written):

1 - Very low novelty: The work largely reproduces known methods or
results with minimal variation.

2 - Low novelty: The work introduces minor extensions or incremental
improvements within an established line of work.

3 - Moderate novelty: The work combines existing ideas in a new way or
applies known methods to a new context.
```

- 4 - High novelty: The work introduces a clearly new methodological, conceptual, or empirical contribution that goes beyond incremental advances.
- 5 - Very high novelty: The work represents a breakthrough or fundamentally new approach that substantially departs from prior work.

TASK:

Step 1 - Prior overlap assessment:

For each prior work, assess whether it:

- a) substantially overlaps with the focal proposal,
- b) partially overlaps, or
- c) is only tangentially related.

Step 2 - Novelty determination:

Based on these overlap assessments, determine whether the focal proposal's main contribution is already present in prior work, partially present, or absent.

Do not infer novelty mechanically from cosine similarity. Use cosine similarity only as contextual supporting information.

Step 3 - Scoring:

Assign a novelty score from 1 to 5 strictly according to the rubric.

PRIOR WORKS (10 closest by cosine similarity, ordered from most to least similar):

Each prior work is provided verbatim (title and abstract).

Cosine similarity reflects semantic similarity to the focal proposal; larger values indicate greater similarity.

Assess each prior only in terms of overlap relative to the focal proposal

OUTPUT REQUIREMENTS:

- Output ONLY valid JSON in the following format:

```
{
  "novel_elements": ["<specific element absent from ALL prior works>",
    "..."],
  "covered_by_prior_art": ["<aspect already present in prior works,
    citing e.g. P3, P7>", "..."],
  "primary_novelty_type": "<conceptual | methodological | problem |
    combinatorial | contextual | none>",
  "rationale": "<1-3 sentences grounded in specific prior works>",
  "novelty_score": <integer from 1 to 5>
}
```

USER_TEMPLATE = ""Evaluate the novelty of the following proposal against the {n} nearest prior publications, applying the rubric and decision rules.

```

=== PROPOSAL ===
Title: {title}
Summary: {abstract}

=== NEAREST PRIOR PUBLICATIONS (most similar first) ===
{neighbors}
"""

NOVELTY_SCHEMA = {
  "name": "novelty_assessment",
  "strict": True,
  "schema": {
    "type": "object",
    "additionalProperties": False,
    "properties": {
      "novel_elements": {
        "type": "array",
        "items": {"type": "string"},
        "description": "Specific elements absent from ALL
          neighbors; [] if none.",
      },
      "covered_by_prior_art": {
        "type": "array",
        "items": {"type": "string"},
        "description": "Aspects already present in neighbors;
          cite pubs e.g. 'P3, P11'."
      },
      "primary_novelty_type": {
        "type": "string",
        "enum": ["conceptual", "methodological", "problem",
          "combinatorial", "contextual", "none"],
      },
      "rationale": {
        "type": "string",
        "description": "1-3 sentences, grounded in specific
          neighbors."
      },
      "novelty_score": {
        "type": "integer",
        "enum": [1, 2, 3, 4, 5],
      },
    },
    "required": ["novel_elements", "covered_by_prior_art",
      "primary_novelty_type", "rationale", "novelty_score"],
  },
}

```

Implementation note: Model deployment was GPT-5.1 via Microsoft Azure batch API, with no reasoning effort (reasoning parameter set to None) and no maximum token limit.

4 Data

We evaluate ORAGINALITY on individual-project proposals submitted to the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) between 2020 and 2022 under its Principal Investigator Projects (*Einzelprojekte*) funding stream. The programme is thematically open, covering all disciplines of basic research, and offers principal investigators and their research groups the resources needed to pursue key research questions over a period of several years, with no restriction on topic or disciplinary focus (Austrian Science Fund, 2025). The sample comprises proposals for which a peer-review novelty score was registered internally. It spans a broad disciplinary range; the most represented fields are biology, medical-theoretical sciences and pharmacy, computer sciences, physics and astronomy, mathematics, and chemistry, reflecting the FWF’s wide disciplinary coverage rather than any selection into specific areas.

For each proposal we observe the title and abstract and human peer-review scores on four official FWF dimensions: originality (novelty), scientific quality, capacity of the research team, and feasibility of the approach. Each proposal received two independent peer reviews, and scores are reported on a 1–5 scale (1 = very low, 5 = very high). We round the mean of the two reviewer scores to the nearest integer and use this rounded value as the working score for each dimension. The present analysis uses the proposal title and abstract as the focal text, encodes them with SPECTER2, computes cosine similarity against the >170 million-publication corpus, and retains the ten closest works published before each proposal’s application date as its prior art.

To frame novelty measurement as a classification problem, we binarise the human originality score. Scores of 1–3 are labelled *Not Highly Novel* (low/medium) and scores of 4–5 *Highly Novel* (high/very high). The target is to identify the Highly Novel class. The evaluation sample comprises $n = 1,252$ proposals, of which 1,091 are labelled Highly Novel and 161 Not Highly Novel by human reviewers.

5 Results

5.1 First-pass classification against human labels

Table 1 reports the classification performance of ORAGINALITY against the original human originality labels, and Table 2 the corresponding confusion matrix. The method is markedly more conservative than human reviewers. It labels 560 of 1,252 proposals (45%) as Highly Novel, against the human rate of 87%. The consequence is a striking asymmetry between precision and recall on the Highly Novel class. Precision is high (0.91). When ORAGINALITY calls a proposal highly novel, human reviewers agree in roughly nine out of ten cases. Recall, however, is only 0.46. The method declines to label as highly novel a large share (584) of proposals that humans rated 4–5.

Table 1: First-pass classification report (ORAGINALITY predictions vs. human originality labels).

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
Not Highly Novel	0.16	0.67	0.25	161
Highly Novel	0.91	0.46	0.61	1,091
Accuracy			0.49	1,252
Macro avg	0.53	0.57	0.43	1,252
Weighted avg	0.81	0.49	0.57	1,252

Table 2: First-pass confusion matrix. Rows: human label; columns: ORAGINALITY prediction.

	Predicted Not Highly Novel	Predicted Highly Novel
Not Highly Novel (human)	108	53
Highly Novel (human)	584	507

Two readings of this asymmetry are possible. On the standard reading, the human labels are ground truth and the 584 cases are false negatives, with ORAGINALITY failing to recognise novelty that is really there. On an alternative reading, ORAGINALITY’s high precision is evidence that, when it does identify novelty, it identifies it correctly; and the 584 “misses” may reflect, at least in part, human over-rating of novelty by reviewers who did not have the same systematic view of prior art. The next subsection provides a diagnostic re-examination of these disagreements.

5.2 Blinded AI re-examination of disagreements

For each of the 584 disagreement cases we conducted a second, blinded LLM re-examination. Each case was presented to two independent models from different providers, GPT-5.1 via Microsoft Azure and Claude Opus 4.8 via Anthropic, using the same prompt. Each model was shown the two competing novelty assessments, one produced by ORAGINALITY (lower novelty) and one corresponding to the human score (higher novelty), without being told which was which, together with the retrieved prior art and the justification produced by ORAGINALITY. It was asked which assessment is more likely correct and, specifically, whether the higher-novelty assessment might have overlooked relevant prior art.

Listing 2: Blinded disagreement-adjudication prompt.

```

SYSTEM_PROMPT = """You are a research methodologist evaluating the
    novelty of a scientific research proposal. You are conducting a post-
    hoc diagnostic analysis.

CONTEXT
You will be shown a research proposal (title and abstract) that received
    two separate novelty reviews, on a 1-5 scale (where 4-5 = high/very
    high novelty, and 3 = medium novelty):

- Review 1 scored the proposal as medium novelty (3) and included a
    written explanation, based on comparing the proposal against its 10
    most semantically similar prior publications (retrieved via embedding
    cosine similarity).
- Review 2 scored the proposal as high or very high novelty (4-5) but did
    not provide a written explanation - only a numeric grade.

You will also be given the list of the 10 prior art works underlying
    Review 1’s explanation, including each work’s title, abstract, cosine
    similarity to the proposal, and publication date.

YOUR TASK
Answer two questions about this proposal:

1. Having read the proposal, Review 1’s explanation, and the prior art
    list, do you agree with Review 1’s explanation - that is, do you think

```

this proposal's contribution is best characterized as medium novelty rather than highly or very highly novel? Answer "yes", "no", or "uncertain", and explain your reasoning in 2-4 sentences, grounded in the specific text provided (the proposal abstract, Review 1's explanation, or specific prior art entries by their prior_art_n label)

2. Independently of question 1: do you think a plausible reason for Review 2's higher score is that Review 2 was not aware of the prior art identified above? Answer "yes" or "no" only - no reasoning needed for this question.

Do not speculate beyond what the provided text supports. If evidence is genuinely ambiguous for question 1, say so rather than inventing certainty.

Return your analysis using only the structured fields defined by the response schema. Do not include any commentary outside those fields

```
REVIEW_DIAGNOSIS_SCHEMA = {
  "type": "object",
  "properties": {
    "project_id": {"type": "string"},
    "agrees_medium_novelty": {"type": "string", "enum": ["yes", "no", "uncertain"]},
    "agreement_reasoning": {"type": "string"},
    "review_2_unaware_of_prior_art": {"type": "string", "enum": ["yes", "no"]},
  },
  "required": [
    "project_id",
    "agrees_medium_novelty",
    "agreement_reasoning",
    "review_2_unaware_of_prior_art",
  ],
  "additionalProperties": False,
}
```

```
RESPONSE_FORMAT = {
  "type": "json_schema",
  "json_schema": {
    "name": "novelty_review_diagnosis",
    "strict": True,
    "schema": REVIEW_DIAGNOSIS_SCHEMA,
  },
}
```

Implementation note: Model deployment was GPT-5.1 via Microsoft Azure batch API, with no reasoning effort (reasoning parameter set to None) and no maximum token limit. Additionally, we ran the same prompt using Claude Opus4.8

The re-examination provides diagnostic evidence consistent with the interpretation that many

first-pass disagreements were driven by incomplete prior-art awareness in the higher-novelty assessment. Table 3 summarises the outcomes for both models. Agreement with the lower-novelty explanation was very high across both providers, though somewhat stronger for GPT-5.1 than for Claude Opus 4.8. GPT-5.1 agreed with the medium/low-novelty explanation in 576 of 584 cases (98.6%) and judged the higher-novelty assessment to have plausibly been made without awareness of relevant prior art in 566 cases (96.9%). Claude Opus 4.8, evaluated on the same 584 cases, agreed with the lower-novelty explanation in 495 cases (84.9%), with a further 24 cases rated as uncertain, and identified incomplete prior-art awareness as a plausible explanation in 408 cases (69.9%). Taken together, both models consistently favour the lower-novelty interpretation when prior art is made explicit, and both attribute disagreements predominantly to incomplete prior-art coverage on the human side rather than to failures of ORAGINALITY to recognise novelty. The difference in rates between the two models reflects differences in calibration rather than a disagreement in direction. This is consistent with the failure mode that ORAGINALITY is designed to address: novelty assessments can be inflated when relevant prior art is incomplete or unavailable to the evaluator. These results should be read as diagnostic evidence about the source of disagreement rather than as an independent validation of the corrected labels.

Table 3: Blinded re-examination of the 584 first-pass disagreements, by model. Each model was shown the two competing novelty assessments without being told which was produced by ORAGINALITY and which by the human reviewer.

	GPT-5.1		Claude Opus 4.8	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Agrees with lower-novelty explanation	576	98.6	495	84.9
Uncertain	—	—	24	4.1
Higher-novelty review unaware of prior art	566	96.9	408	69.9

Note. Base $n = 584$ disagreement cases. Two cases returned missing values for Claude Opus 4.8 and are excluded from percentage calculations for that model. The uncertain category applies only to the first question; the second question required a yes/no answer.

5.2.1 Reconciled performance

As an illustrative diagnostic exercise, we re-label as Not Highly Novel the 495 cases in which Claude Opus 4.8, the more conservative of the two adjudicators, favoured the lower-novelty assessment. Table 4 and Table 5 show the implied performance. Note that ORAGINALITY’s predictions are unchanged throughout; what changes is the reference standard against which they are scored. Under this more conservative reconciliation, the implied overall accuracy would be 0.89. Both classes remain reasonably well identified, with precision and recall of 0.91 and 0.85 for Highly Novel proposals, and 0.87 and 0.92 for Not Highly Novel proposals.

We emphasise what this number does and does not establish. It is not an independent out-of-sample accuracy because the revised labels are produced by an LLM adjudicator. The reconciliation should therefore be read as a *hypothesis* about the source of the first-pass disagreements, namely that they are dominated by human novelty over-ratings caused by incomplete prior art on the human side, rather than as a validated ground truth. The choice to use the more conservative adjudicator for this exercise reflects a deliberate preference for a lower-bound illustration of the potential improvement.

Table 4: Reconciled classification report, after re-labelling the 495 disagreements flagged by Claude Opus 4.8 as Not Highly Novel. ORAGINALITY predictions are unchanged; only the reference labels are revised.

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
Not Highly Novel	0.87	0.92	0.89	656
Highly Novel	0.91	0.85	0.88	596
Accuracy			0.89	1,252
Macro avg	0.89	0.89	0.89	1,252
Weighted avg	0.89	0.89	0.89	1,252

Table 5: Reconciled confusion matrix. Rows: revised reference label; columns: ORAGINALITY prediction.

	Predicted Not Highly Novel	Predicted Highly Novel
Not Highly Novel (revised)	603	53
Highly Novel (revised)	89	507

5.2.2 Expert audit of disagreement cases

The re-examination in Section 5.2 relies on LLM adjudicators, so it cannot by itself rule out the possibility that both the scoring and the adjudication share a common machine bias. To address this directly, we conducted a manual audit with six independent expert researchers spanning a range of fields and career stages: Britt Anderson (psychology, University of Waterloo), Marco Peres (materials science, IST Lisbon), Ana Machado (oceanography, University of Lisbon), Maria Bampa (machine learning for health, Stockholm University), Carlos Vergara (astrophysics, University of Sussex), and Todd Cook (astrophysics, University of Sussex).

Each expert reviewed a set of disagreement cases drawn from areas close to their own expertise. Because funded projects and their descriptions are publicly available, only successful proposals were included, so that no confidential material left FWF. Within these, we included only cases of proposals that human reviewers scored as highly novel but that ORAGINALITY scored as moderately novel. For each case, experts were shown the proposal title and abstract, the titles and abstracts of the ten closest prior-art publications, the ORAGINALITY rationale comparing the proposal with that prior art, and the separate agreement reasoning produced by the blinded re-examination. Across twelve cases in total, experts were asked whether they agreed that the proposal was better characterised as moderately rather than highly novel, given the rationale and the prior art. At this first stage they were not shown the exact scoring rubric used by the system.

The experts unanimously found the rationale highly informative for novelty assessment and well constructed. In every reviewed case they judged the retrieved prior art to be relevant and the argument linking the proposal to that prior art to be clear and well reasoned, describing the output as a useful way to understand what is actually new in a proposal relative to existing work. In most cases they also agreed with the substantive decision to treat the proposal as moderately rather than highly novel. There were two exceptions. In one case a reviewer felt the rationale could still support a higher novelty level, and in another a reviewer agreed with the rationale but felt the conclusion should be lower than moderate.

These two cases proved instructive. After a follow-up discussion in which the scoring rubric was shared, both reviewers came to agree with the system’s assessment. The discussion surfaced a

recurring theme that bears directly on the interpretation of human novelty scores. Experts noted that at times it is very hard to disentangle the novelty of an idea from its quality, robustness, and merit. A moderately novel idea can completely deserve funding if it promises high value to the literature. A common case is combinatorial novelty, where an established method or concept is applied to a new but closely related context, such as a different population subgroup, geographic setting, or material. The novelty here comes entirely from the change of context, while the underlying method and concept are unchanged. Such work can be valuable and well worth funding, since extending a known approach to a new setting often produces useful results, but it remains a predictable and low-risk recombination of existing elements and should score lower on novelty than work that introduces a genuinely new method or concept, or that combines existing elements in an unexpected, ambitious, or high-risk way. A reviewer who values the proposal’s potential contribution may nonetheless rate it as highly novel, conflating its expected value with its actual degree of departure from prior art. The reverse case is equally telling. A highly novel idea may not deserve funding if it is poorly constructed, highly implausible, or unlikely to add much value even if it succeeds. Here a reviewer wary of the proposal’s weaknesses may rate it as less novel, again merging a judgement of quality with a judgement of novelty. Because novelty and quality are scored within the same evaluation that determines funding, reviewers often face an implicit incentive to conflate them, that is, to rate a high-quality proposal as more novel so as not to reduce its chances, or a weak proposal as less novel so as to justify rejecting it. The human novelty score is therefore not always a clean measure of novelty alone, but a composite that absorbs judgements of merit. This consideration complements the earlier point about prior-art coverage. Reviewers may over-rate novelty both because they do not always have complete access to or awareness of the relevant prior art, and because novelty and quality are difficult to separate in practice. The two mechanisms can operate together, and both push human novelty scores upward relative to a measure that compares the proposal against explicitly retrieved prior art under a rubric that isolates novelty. This is consistent with the broader peer-review literature on conservatism and the entanglement of evaluation criteria (Boudreau et al., 2016; Lane et al., 2022; Stephan et al., 2017), and it offers a concrete mechanism for the over-rating pattern documented above.

A measure that assesses novelty against explicitly retrieved prior art, under a rubric that defines novelty independently of quality, can separate what human review tends to merge. This points toward a broader design direction that emerged from the discussion. Rather than a single model producing a single score, novelty assessment could form one component of an orchestrated, multi-agent review system, in which separate specialised agents assess novelty, quality, feasibility, and other dimensions independently, and an orchestrating process combines them. It would then remain for funding agencies and human decision-makers to decide which dimensions to prioritise, and what trade-offs between, for example, novelty and quality, are acceptable at the margin. By keeping the dimensions transparently separate, such a system could make explicit the trade-offs that human reviewers currently make implicitly, and ORAGINALITY provides a concrete, validated instrument for the novelty component.

6 Validation test: comparison with the 1000 Ideas programme

The results in Section 5 assess ORAGINALITY against human peer-review labels on PI Projects proposals. A complementary validation strategy is to test whether the indicator assigns higher novelty scores to proposals from a programme explicitly designed to attract high-risk, high-reward research. If the measure captures what it claims to capture, such proposals should score systematically higher than those from a mainstream funding stream. The FWF 1000 Ideas programme provides a

well-suited testbed.

The programme was created to support radically novel, high-risk, high-reward basic research that is unlikely to be funded through conventional peer-reviewed schemes. It offers small, time-limited grants to explore bold ideas at an early stage and uses double-blind assessment combined with partial randomisation to reduce bias and increase tolerance for unconventional proposals. A recent independent evaluation, conducted by Technopolis Group and commissioned by FWF, assessed the programme using a mixed-methods approach combining applicant and awardee surveys, qualitative interviews, programme data, and econometric analysis of bibliometric outcomes, with the PI Projects stream serving as a benchmark. The evaluation found broad qualitative and quantitative evidence that the programme succeeds in attracting and supporting research of a distinctly different character from mainstream FWF funding, with proposals and outputs consistently described as more exploratory, more unconventional, and more willing to depart from established approaches (Vingre et al., 2026). This makes the 1000 Ideas applicant pool a meaningful external reference: a group of proposals that independent evaluation evidence suggests are more novel, on average, than the PI Projects population used to develop and assess ORAGINALITY.

The combined sample used for the validation analysis comprises 1,650 proposals: 398 from the 1000 Ideas programme, all from 2020, and 1,252 from the PI Projects stream, covering 2020 to 2022. The two samples differ in disciplinary composition. Biology, computer sciences, medical-theoretical sciences and pharmacy, and clinical medicine are relatively more prominent in the 1000 Ideas sample, while mathematics, physics and astronomy, geosciences, and linguistics and literature are comparatively stronger in the PI Projects sample. All comparisons are conducted with field and year fixed effects to account for these compositional and temporal differences. To address the residual temporal mismatch between the two samples, we additionally run the analysis restricting the PI Projects sample to 2020 only.

The distribution of ORAGINALITY novelty scores for the 1000 Ideas sample is concentrated in the medium to high range. No proposals received a score of 1, and only four (1.0%) received a score of 2. The remaining proposals split almost evenly between scores of 3 (48.1%) and 4 (50.9%), with none scoring 5. Just over half were rated as highly novel by ORAGINALITY.

6.1 Validation results

To test whether 1000 Ideas proposals score higher on novelty than PI Projects proposals, we estimate a logit model with a binary outcome equal to one if the ORAGINALITY score is 4 or above, and a 1000 Ideas indicator as the key regressor. Table 6 reports results across six specifications: standard logit and Firth penalised logit for the full sample and the 2020-only sample, and wild cluster bootstrap for inference under small and imbalanced field clusters.

Across all specifications, 1000 Ideas proposals have significantly higher odds of receiving a high novelty score than PI Projects proposals. The estimated odds ratio is stable across estimators and samples, ranging from 1.74 to 1.89. The result holds under Firth penalised logit, which corrects for potential small-sample bias in fields with perfect prediction, and under wild cluster bootstrap, which accounts for the small number of field clusters. Restricting the sample to 2020, which removes the temporal mismatch between the two programmes, yields slightly larger point estimates and similarly strong inference, with a bootstrap p-value of 0.006.

An odds ratio of approximately 1.8 means that, within the same field and year, a 1000 Ideas proposal is roughly 80% more likely than a PI Projects proposal to receive a high novelty score from ORAGINALITY. Given that the 1000 Ideas programme was specifically designed to attract research that conventional funding schemes would not support, and that an independent evaluation found broad evidence of its success in doing so (Vingre et al., 2026), this difference is consistent with what

Table 6: Logit estimates of the probability of a high novelty score (`ORAGINALITY` ≥ 4). The key regressor is an indicator for 1000 Ideas proposals (d_ti). Odds ratios reported throughout.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Logit	Firth	Logit	Logit	Firth	Logit
	All	All	All+Boot	2020	2020	2020+Boot
d_ti	1.765*** (0.304)	1.740*** (0.296)	1.737*** (0.299)	1.884*** (0.358)	1.824*** (0.338)	1.889*** (0.359)
Observations	1,639	1,650	1,649	682	693	690
Wild bootstrap p			0.002			0.006

Note. Field and year fixed effects included in full-sample specifications. Only field fixed effects included in 2020-only specifications as year is constant. Fields with fewer than ten observations collapsed into an Other category for bootstrap specifications. Standard errors in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

a valid novelty indicator should detect. The result provides external support for `ORAGINALITY` as a measure that tracks meaningful differences in the novelty profile of research proposals, beyond its agreement with human peer-review labels on the PI Projects sample.

Table 7 reports OLS estimates using the continuous `ORAGINALITY` novelty score as the outcome, providing a complementary picture to the logit results.

Table 7: OLS estimates of the `ORAGINALITY` novelty score. The key regressor is an indicator for 1000 Ideas proposals (d_ti).

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	OLS All	OLS All+Boot	OLS 2020	OLS 2020+Boot
d_ti	0.130*** (0.041)	0.130*** (0.041)	0.144*** (0.046)	0.144*** (0.046)
Observations	1,649	1,649	692	692
R-squared	0.067	0.067	0.079	0.079
Wild bootstrap p		0.005		0.006

Note. Field and year fixed effects included in full-sample specifications. Only field fixed effects included in 2020-only specifications as year is constant. Wild bootstrap p-values clustered by field of science. Standard errors in parentheses.

* $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

The OLS results confirm the pattern from the logit analysis. Within the same field and year, 1000 Ideas proposals score on average 0.13 points higher on the `ORAGINALITY` novelty scale than PI Projects proposals. Restricting the sample to 2020 yields a slightly larger estimate of 0.14 points. Both estimates are robust to wild cluster bootstrap inference, with p-values below 0.01. Given that the novelty scale runs from 1 to 5, a difference of 0.13 to 0.14 points represents a consistent and statistically robust gap, complementing the odds ratio finding that 1000 Ideas proposals are substantially more likely to cross the high-novelty threshold.

7 Discussion

7.1 Interpretation

The first-pass results are consistent with what grounding and rubric together are designed to produce, namely well-calibrated strictness rather than directional preference. ORAGINALITY is conservative about awarding the “highly novel” label, but when it does award it, it is almost always in agreement with the human review (precision 0.91). The re-examination suggests that at least part of this conservatism may reflect correction rather than error. In most disagreements, the model identified an overlap with prior art that the human assessment had plausibly missed. This finding is consistent with the broader literature on conservatism and incomplete information in human review (Boudreau et al., 2016; Lane et al., 2022; Stephan et al., 2017) and with the embedding-based result that novelty is legible in the semantic distance to prior art (Machado, 2025).

The re-examination was conducted independently using two models from different providers, GPT-5.1 and Claude Opus 4.8. Both consistently favoured the lower-novelty interpretation when prior art was made explicit, attributing most disagreements to incomplete prior-art coverage on the human side rather than to failures of ORAGINALITY. Claude Opus 4.8 was more conservative in its agreement rates, which provides a useful lower bound on the diagnostic conclusion: even under the more cautious adjudicator, the direction of the finding is the same. Convergence across two independent, high-performance models from different providers strengthens confidence in the interpretation, while the difference in rates serves as a reminder that the reconciled accuracy figures should be read as illustrative rather than definitive. A manual audit by six independent experts provides additional validation that does not depend on any LLM. Experts found the retrieval-grounded rationales highly informative and well constructed, and in the great majority of reviewed cases agreed that the proposals were better characterised as moderately rather than highly novel. The audit also surfaced a second mechanism behind human rating, namely the difficulty of separating novelty from quality, which complements the prior-art-coverage mechanism identified by the blinded re-examination.

The validation test against the 1000 Ideas programme adds a further layer of support that is independent of the human peer-review labels used to assess ORAGINALITY in the first place. Proposals submitted to a programme specifically designed to attract high-risk, high-reward research receive systematically higher novelty scores than PI Projects proposals within the same field and year, with an odds ratio of approximately 1.8 and a mean score difference of around 0.13 points on the continuous scale. This pattern holds across estimators and is robust to restricting the comparison to 2020 only. Since the novelty premium of the 1000 Ideas programme has been independently confirmed through qualitative and quantitative evaluation evidence (Vingre et al., 2026), the ability of ORAGINALITY to detect it provides external support for the measure beyond its agreement with individual reviewer labels.

The contrast with the earlier bias result (Machado, 2026) is the central point. There, an *ungrounded* LLM, left to compare proposals under a general prompt, diverged from humans precisely on novelty and in the conservative direction, reflecting a subjective preference. Here, a *grounded* LLM, forced to compare the focal text against a systematically retrieved and time-valid body of prior art under an explicit rubric, produces high-precision novelty judgements whose disagreements with humans appear to be informative rather than biased, and whose scores track meaningful differences in the novelty profile of research programmes. The difference between the two regimes is operationalisation. By fixing what prior art is and what novelty means, the assessment becomes a measurement rather than a judgement.

7.2 Design principles and implications for AI-assisted evaluation

The results support a clear design principle for LLM-assisted research evaluation, namely that novelty assessment should never be left to the model’s implicit judgement. Retrieving prior art from semantic content rather than from reference lists is central to this. The retrieved set is constructed the same way for every text, so the measure does not inherit differences in referencing conventions across fields or venues. It surfaces the most similar prior work whether or not the author chose to cite it, making the comparison independent of author citation behaviour. And the only way to change the retrieved prior art is to change the content of the idea itself, which makes the measure hard to game. This last property matters increasingly as strategic citation behaviour and AI-generated hallucinations erode the reliability of reference-based indicators (Kojaku et al., 2021; Zhao et al., 2026).

Used this way, an LLM is not a black-box efficient reviewer but a transparent instrument. The rubric ties the score to observable overlap with concretely identified prior art, and the justification records which prior-art items drove the assessment, making the reasoning inspectable and contestable. This also reframes disagreement with human reviewers as a potentially useful signal. A flagged overlap that a human missed is actionable, whereas an opaque score is not.

7.3 Limitations and future research

ORAGINALITY aims to approximate the kind of qualitative judgment that expert reviewers apply when assessing novelty, while enabling scalable and automated assessment with minimal manual input. Expert evaluators typically judge novelty through close reading, comparison with the most relevant prior work, and qualitative assessment of how far a contribution departs from what came before in concept, method, or empirical approach. The proposed methodology mirrors this process by grounding novelty assessment in publication text and by defining prior art as the most semantically similar earlier contributions.

The approach relies on titles and abstracts as the most information-dense and widely available representations of scientific work. By systematically identifying and presenting the closest prior art, the framework moves beyond indirect proxies such as journal cross-referencing, subject categories, and predefined taxonomies, as well as approaches based solely on word counts or single scalar semantic distance metrics. It also reduces sensitivity to mechanical differences in referencing and writing practices that can distort novelty measures. Indicators based on new combinations of referenced journals or terms tend to reward publications with longer reference lists or more verbose descriptions, conflating stylistic or disciplinary conventions with intellectual originality. The proposed framework instead evaluates novelty through relative semantic comparison with the most relevant prior work, limiting the influence of text length, citation volume, and writing style on the resulting assessment.

Despite these strengths, several limitations apply. First, the reconciled accuracy figures are computed against labels that LLM adjudicators helped define. Two mitigations reduce this concern. The use of two independent models from different providers shows that the direction of the finding does not depend on a single system, with the more conservative Claude Opus 4.8 figures serving as a lower bound. Moreover, the manual audit in Section 5.2.2 provides human validation independent of any LLM. That audit was nonetheless limited to twelve proposals in the experts’ own fields, so a larger and more systematic expert evaluation, spanning unfunded proposals and the opposite direction of disagreement, remains valuable future work.

Second, the measure is only as good as the retrieved prior art. Coverage gaps in the publication corpus, the reliance on titles and abstracts rather than full text, and the fixed cutoff at ten retrieved

items all bound performance. Future work should vary the number of retrieved items, compare results against full-text representations where available, and test the approach against bibliometric novelty indicators based on atypical combinations of references (Uzzi et al., 2013; Lee et al., 2015).

Third, binarising a 1 to 5 originality score at the boundary between 3 and 4 is a modelling choice. The human originality score is itself a noisy signal, averaged across two reviewers. Robustness to alternative thresholds is worth examining in future work.

Fourth, the label-based evaluation covers a single funder. The validation test against the 1000 Ideas programme offers some external support, showing that ORAGINALITY detects meaningful differences in the novelty profile of research programmes independently of peer-review labels. That said, both samples come from the same funder and the same national context. Replication across agencies, disciplines, and time periods remains an important next step, as does downstream analysis linking ORAGINALITY scores to publication and citation outcomes, to assess whether the measure captures novelty that matters beyond the proposal stage.

More broadly, the framework functions as a large-scale screening tool rather than a replacement for in-depth human evaluation. Reliance on titles and abstracts provides only a condensed view of a scientific contribution and omits the methodological detail, empirical nuance, and argumentative structure that expert reviewers consider when reading full texts. Novelty scores are therefore best understood as inputs to portfolio-level evaluations and exploratory assessments, helping to surface patterns and areas of interest, not as automated decisions about individual proposals.

8 Conclusion

LLMs are entering research evaluation quickly, and the evidence that they mishandle novelty is accumulating. We have argued that this is not an immutable property of the technology but a consequence of how the task is posed. An ungrounded model judges novelty by preference and cannot reliably reason about what counts as prior art. ORAGINALITY reposes the task. By retrieving, for each focal text, a systematic and time-valid body of prior art from semantic content rather than from gameable reference lists, and by scoring novelty against that prior art under an explicit rubric, it turns an ambiguous judgement into a transparent measurement.

On 1,252 FWF PI Projects proposals, ORAGINALITY identifies highly novel work with high precision, and a blinded re-examination conducted independently with two models from different providers suggests that many apparent misses may be human over-ratings traceable to incomplete prior art. An initial manual audit by independent experts supports this interpretation, and scaling that validation is the key next step. A validation test against the FWF 1000 Ideas programme, designed specifically to attract high-risk, high-reward research, shows that ORAGINALITY assigns systematically higher novelty scores to that programme’s proposals than to mainstream PI Projects proposals within the same field and year, providing external support for the measure that is independent of peer-review labels.

The broader lesson is that trustworthy LLM novelty assessment requires operationalisation. Grounding the comparison in retrieved prior art, imposing temporal validity, and anchoring the score to an explicit rubric are what replace subjective preference with systematic measurement.

Data availability

The data underlying this study were made available by FWF under a confidentiality agreement. The titles and abstracts and reviewer scores are confidential and cannot be shared by the author.

Acknowledgements

The author thanks the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) for providing the proposal and peer-review data used in this study. Access to this data was a byproduct of Technopolis Group’s process evaluation of the FWF Emerging Fields programme, during which different approaches to novelty measurement were explored using FWF Principal Investigator Projects data and 1000 Ideas for benchmarking purposes. The application presented in this paper was developed through that exploration. The author is grateful to Britt Anderson, Maria Bampa, Marco Peres, Ana Machado, Carlos Vergara, and Todd Cook for their expert review of disagreement cases.

Author contributions

The author is solely responsible for all aspects of this work, including conception, data curation, analysis, and writing.

GenAI

Generative AI models are themselves the object and instrument of this study. The novelty assessment method described here uses GPT-5.1 (via Microsoft Azure), and the blinded re-examination of disagreements uses both GPT-5.1 (via Microsoft Azure) and Claude Opus 4.8 (via Anthropic, under a zero data retention agreement), as documented in Sections 3 and 5. Beyond this methodological use, generative AI tools were used to assist with routine copy editing of the manuscript. The author takes full responsibility for the content of the paper.

References

- FWF Austrian Science Fund. Principal investigator projects. <https://www.fwf.ac.at/en/funding/portfolio/projects/principal-investigator-projects>, 2025. Accessed June 2026.
- Emily M. Bender, Timnit Gebru, Angelina McMillan-Major, and Shmargaret Shmitchell. On the dangers of stochastic parrots: Can language models be too big? In *Proceedings of the 2021 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT)*, pages 610–623, 2021. doi: 10.1145/3442188.3445922.
- Kevin J. Boudreau, Eva C. Guinan, Karim R. Lakhani, and Christoph Riedl. Looking across and looking beyond the knowledge frontier: Intellectual distance, novelty, and resource allocation in science. *Management Science*, 62(10):2765–2783, 2016. doi: 10.1287/mnsc.2015.2285.
- Arman Cohan, Sergey Feldman, Iz Beltagy, Doug Downey, and Daniel S. Weld. SPECTER: Document-level representation learning using citation-informed transformers. In *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*, pages 2270–2282, 2020. doi: 10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.207.
- Liangping Ding, Cornelia Lawson, and Philip Shapira. Rise of generative artificial intelligence in science. *Scientometrics*, 130:5093–5114, 2025. doi: 10.1007/s11192-025-05413-z.
- Frontiers. Unlocking AI’s untapped potential: Responsible innovation in research and publishing. Whitepaper, Frontiers, 2025.

- Sadamori Kojaku, Giacomo Livan, and Naoki Masuda. Detecting anomalous citation groups in journal networks. *Scientific Reports*, 11:14524, 2021. doi: 10.1038/s41598-021-93572-3.
- Peter Kolarz and Diogo Machado. Inside the funding process: Using generative AI to assess reviewers’ criteria prioritisation in multi-stage application assessments. *fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation*, 57(e18):1–25, 2025. doi: 10.22163/fteval.2025.710.
- Max Kozlov. Grant proposals drafted with AI help more likely to win NIH funding. *Nature*, 2026. doi: 10.1038/d41586-026-00369-3.
- Jacqueline N. Lane, Misha Teplitskiy, Gary Gray, Hardeep Ranu, Michael Menietti, Eva C. Guinan, and Karim R. Lakhani. Conservatism gets funded? a field experiment on the role of negative information in novel project evaluation. *Management Science*, 68(6):4478–4495, 2022. doi: 10.1287/mnsc.2021.4107.
- You-Na Lee, John P. Walsh, and Jian Wang. Creativity in scientific teams: Unpacking novelty and impact. *Research Policy*, 44(3):684–697, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.respol.2014.10.007.
- Patrick Lewis, Ethan Perez, Aleksandra Piktus, Fabio Petroni, Vladimir Karpukhin, Naman Goyal, Heinrich Küttler, Mike Lewis, Wen-tau Yih, Tim Rocktäschel, Sebastian Riedel, and Douwe Kiela. Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive NLP tasks. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, volume 33, pages 9459–9474, 2020. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2005.11401.
- Ethan Lin, Zhiyuan Peng, and Yi Fang. Evaluating and enhancing large language models for novelty assessment in scholarly publications. In *Proceedings of the 1st Workshop on AI and Scientific Discovery: Directions and Opportunities*, pages 46–57, Albuquerque, New Mexico, USA, May 2025. Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/2025.aisd-main.5. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2025.aisd-main.5/>.
- Diogo Machado. Quantitative indicators for high-risk/high-reward research. *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Working Papers*, (2021/07), 2021. doi: 10.1787/675cbef6-en.
- Diogo Machado. The geometry of scientific novelty: a novelty vector from LLM embedding geometry. Paper presented at the 10th Atlanta Conference on Science and Innovation Policy, session “Novelty in Innovation”, May 2025.
- Diogo Machado. Generative AI bias against scientific novelty: a cautionary tale from a small-sample evaluation of research proposals. Paper presented at the EU-SPRI Forum Conference 2026, session “AI in S&I Policy 4: Integrating AI in science and innovation policy. Opportunities and risks”, June 2026.
- Yian Qian, Zhicheng Wen, Alexander C. Furnas, Yi Bai, Eric Shao, and Dashun Wang. The rise of large language models and the direction and impact of US federal research funding. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2601.15485*, 2026. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2601.15485.
- Simra Shahid, Marissa Radensky, Raymond Fok, Pao Siangliulue, Daniel S. Weld, and Tom Hope. Literature-grounded novelty assessment of scientific ideas. In *Proceedings of the Fifth Workshop on Scholarly Document Processing (SDP 2025)*, pages 96–113, Vienna, Austria, July 2025. Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/2025.sdp-1.9. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2025.sdp-1.9/>.

- Hyunjoo Shin, Jian Tang, Yejin Lee, et al. Mind the blind spots: A focus-level evaluation framework for LLM reviews. In *Proceedings of the 2025 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, pages 35630–35656, 2025. doi: 10.18653/v1/2025.emnlp-main.1805.
- Amanpreet Singh, Mike D’Arcy, Arman Cohan, Doug Downey, and Sergey Feldman. SciRepEval: A multi-format benchmark for scientific document representations. In *Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, 2023. doi: 10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.338.
- Paula Stephan, Reinhilde Veugelers, and Jian Wang. Reviewers are blinkered by bibliometrics. *Nature*, 544(7651):411–412, 2017. doi: 10.1038/544411a.
- Brian Uzzi, Satyam Mukherjee, Michael Stringer, and Ben Jones. Atypical combinations and scientific impact. *Science*, 342(6157):468–472, 2013. doi: 10.1126/science.1240474.
- Anete Vingre, Diogo Machado, Florentine Frantz, Rima Martin, Laura Sutinen, and Erik Arnold. Evaluation of the Austrian Science Fund (FWF) 1000 Ideas programme. Programme evaluation, Technopolis Group, 2026.
- Wei Wu, Chao Zhang, Yang Zhao, et al. Impact of large language models on peer review opinions from a fine-grained perspective: Evidence from top conference proceedings in AI. *Scientometrics*, 131:3547–3584, 2026. doi: 10.1007/s11192-026-05645-7.
- Ming Zhang, Kexin Tan, Yueyuan Huang, Yujiong Shen, Chunchun Ma, Li Ju, Xinran Zhang, Yuhui Wang, Wenqing Jing, Jingyi Deng, Huayu Sha, Binze Hu, Jingqi Tong, Changhao Jiang, Yage Geng, Yuankai Ying, Yue Zhang, Zhangyue Yin, Zhiheng Xi, Shihan Dou, Tao Gui, Qi Zhang, and Xuanjing Huang. Opennovelty: An llm-powered agentic system for verifiable scholarly novelty assessment, 2026. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2601.01576>.
- Zhenyue Zhao, Yihe Wang, Toby Stuart, Mathijs De Vaan, Paul Ginsparg, and Yian Yin. LLM hallucinations in the wild: Large-scale evidence from non-existent citations. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2605.07723*, 2026. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2605.07723.
- Zhiyuan Zhu, Yusheng Liao, Zhe Chen, Yuhao Wang, Yunfeng Guan, Yanfeng Wang, and Yu Wang. EvolveBench: A comprehensive benchmark for assessing temporal awareness in LLMs on evolving knowledge. In *Proceedings of the 63rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*, pages 16173–16188, Vienna, Austria, July 2025. Association for Computational Linguistics. ISBN 979-8-89176-251-0. doi: 10.18653/v1/2025.acl-long.788.